

FRUIT PEELS AS A SUSTAINABLE WASTE FOR BIOSORPTION OF HEAVY METAL WASTEWATER

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Abstract. A technique called biosorption employing Fruit Peel Waste has showed great promise in the removal of various organic and inorganic pollutants from aqueous effluents. It is advised to employ biosorbents, such as Fruit Peel Waste, since they are readily available, reasonably priced, as well as have a good capacity for adsorption of a variety of contaminants. Researchers' various surface modification techniques are helpful for increasing adsorption capacity. The use of Fruit Peel Waste in batch adsorption studies, which offers fundamental information to build an adsorption column for industrial purposes. Over 95% of metal ions are observed to desorb. Over five to six cycles, the researchers maintained an adsorption effectiveness of over 90% using Fruit Peel Waste. Fruit Peel Waste can be burned safely and its heating value used once the metal ions have been recovered. To remove metal ions from fruit peel waste, a variety of substances were employed in varying amounts, including NaOH, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, and HCl. Fruit Peel Waste has a lot of potential for treating wastewater because it is readily available and reasonably priced, despite the results' low repeatability. Fruit peel waste can be utilised to remove colours and heavy metals, but further research is needed to remove organic and gaseous contaminants.

Keywords: sustainable, Fruit Peel Waste, Biosorption, wastewater.

Introduction

Heavy metal pollution

Metallic elements with a density that is higher than that of water are referred to as heavy metals [1]. Heavy metals that can cause toxicity at low levels of exposure are thought to be related to both heaviness and toxicity [2]. Environmental pollution by these metals has been a growing global public health and ecological problem in recent years. Additionally, because of their exponential growth in a variety of industrial, agricultural, home, and technology uses, human exposure has increased considerably [3]. The environment is known to include heavy metals from geogenic, industrial, agricultural, pharmacological, residential effluent, and atmospheric sources. Point source industries including mining, smelters, and foundries, as well as other metal-based industrial operations, are major sources of environmental pollution [4].

Wastewater Treatment:

Wastewater treatment is the process of removing wastewater from inhabited regions and turning it into a harmless form in order to safeguard human health. After being properly cleaned, wastewater can either be recycled for home and industrial use to reduce the demand for freshwater or released back into the aquatic environment, adding to the world's natural water reserve. Reducing the amount of water that humans use is thought to be possible through wastewater treatment. However, the efficiency with which wastewater can be recycled and reused will largely

depend on the technologies used and how well they work to turn wastewater into safe drinking water [5].

Introduction to Biosorption:

Biosorption is a complex process that occurs through a range of mechanisms, such as ion exchange, surface complexation, adsorption, absorption, and precipitation. It is not dependent on metabolism. In the environment and in traditional biotreatment procedures, biosorption processes are crucial. Biosorption is a subfield of biotechnology that deals with the extraction or recovery of both organic & inorganic materials from solutions using biological material. This can include seaweeds, plant materials, dead or living microorganisms and their parts, natural residues, industrial and agricultural wastes, and seaweeds. Biosorption has been hailed for decades as a promising and affordable clean-up technique. Thus far, commercialisation of biosorption technology has been limited despite a huge rise in publications in this research area and significant advances in our knowledge of this complicated phenomenon [6].

Rationale for using Fruit Peels:

Vegetable and fruit peels, which are inexpensive adsorbents because they have high metal adsorption capabilities and a large number of surface functional groups, have become attractive agricultural waste products. These easily obtainable plant-based substances, such as plant fibres and other debris, provide economical and effective sorbents for metal ions. By using plant-based byproducts as metal sorbents, green chemistry and the circular bioeconomy are supported, providing both environmentally and commercially feasible solutions. To improve adsorption stability and efficiency, pretreatment could be necessary before using them. One potential use for plant fibres is as an inexpensive biowaste for the adsorption of heavy metals from acid mine drainage produced by the mining industry, or from contaminated water. Using this technique, fibres can draw in and hold onto heavy metal ions in a bioreactor by acting as adsorbents [7].

2. Mechanism of Biosorption

The physicochemical interactions between the metal and the functional groups on the surface of the biosorbent cause the biosorption of heavy metals and organic molecules. The non-metabolic processes that are involved are chemical sorption, ion exchange, and physical adsorption [8].

3. Factors Affecting Biosorption Efficiency

Much emphasis has been paid to biosorption, an economical and environmentally beneficial way of eliminating heavy metal pollution from the environment. This removes heavy metals and other dangerous chemicals from industrial effluents and other wastes that are directly released into the environment by using biological sources like microbial and agricultural biomass. Temperature, pH, biomass concentration, initial ion concentration, contact time, agitation rate, type of biosorbent, and competing ions are some of the variables that affect efficiency. Biosorbents can originate from microbial sources or plant biomass through various methods [9].

4. Types of fruit peels used in biosorption

Citrus Peels (e.g., Orange, Lemon): Orange residue, a by-product of the fruit industry, is primarily utilised as animal feed. Oranges (*Citrus sp.*) are one of the citrus that are abundant in India. Orange residue, or citrus fruit residue, consists of pulp (the portion removed from the juice) and peel. It is mostly made up of low molecular weight substances like limonene, cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin, and pectin (galacturonic acid). The main constituents of these fractions are, in that order, pectin, cellulose, hemicelluloses, fat, a small amount of nitrogen compound, and

approximately 3% ash. The most common kind of polysaccharide found in orange residue's cell walls is pectic compounds. Orange peels have been utilised in the adsorption process and are known to be an agro-industrial residue having adsorptive qualities based on literature [10].

Banana Peels: Given its abundance and inexpensive cost, banana peel is a choice among many and fascinating biomass materials for creating new biosorbents. Bananas rank fourth in the world in terms of cultivation, and their peel waste is easily accessible, underutilised, and useful in commercial settings. As a result, there is significant business interest in recycling this material to remove organic contaminants from contaminated water. In two relatively recent studies [13, 14], the use of dried banana peel powder (BPP) as a biosorbent material has been investigated for the decontamination of wastewater, primarily in the removal of textile colours [11], heavy metals [12], and other types of contaminants. The majority of research on biosorbents made from banana peels has demonstrated effective biosorbent reuse for up to five cycles and above [15].

Mango: Member of the Anacardiaceae family is the mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). Its remarkable colour, flavour, and perfume, along with its great nutritional, phytochemical, and medicinal worth make it one of the most significant and well-liked tropical fruits. The inedible byproducts are disposed of, while the edible portion is primarily industrially processed into different pulps or juices. However, mango peels and other by-products are a valuable source of physiologically active chemicals that have a variety of uses. By-products from mangos makels. around 35–55% of the overall mass. Additionally, if they are used more, they might lessen waste production and environmental harm [16].

There are many other fruit peels too which are efficient in the removal of heavy metals such as lemon (*Citrus limón*), guava (*Psidium guajava*), tree tomato (*Solanum betaceum*), blackberry (*Rubus ulmifolius*), pineapple (*Ananas comosus*), passion fruit (*Passiflora edulis*), orange (*Citrus sinensis*), coconut (*Cocos nucifera*), avocado (*Persea americana*), papaya (*Carica papaya*), apple (*Malus pumila*), lulo (*Solanum quitoense*), tangerine (*Citrus reticulata*), soursop (*Anona muricata*), strawberry (*Fragaria spp*), curuba (*Passiflora tarminiana*), melon (*Cucumis melo*), watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*), grape (*Vitis vinifera*), passion fruit (*Passiflora ligularis*), borojo (*Alibertia patinoi*), pear (*Pyrus communis*), plum (*Prunus doméstica*), papayuela (*Vasconcellea pubescens*), loquat (*Achras sapote*), peach (*Prunus pérsica*), mamoncillo (*Melicoccus bijugatus*), sapote (*Pouteria sapota*), uchuva (*Physalis peruviana*), chontaduro (*Bactris gasipaes*), bananito (*Musa AA Si- monds*), feijoa (*Acca sellowiana*), cherry (*Prunus subg. Cerasus*), carambolo (*Averrhoa carambola*), kiwi (*Actinidia deliciosa*), guama (*Inga edulis*), grapefruit (*Citrus aurantium*), badea (*Passiflora quadrangularis*), arazá (*Azara*), noni (*Morinda citrifolia*), fig (*Ficus carica*), cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*), mamey (*Pouteria sapota*), lime (*Citrus aurantiifolia*), custard apple (*Annona cherimola*), pomarrosa (*Syzygium jambos*), pitahaya (*Selenicereus undatus*), mangosteen (*Garcinia mangostana*), copoazú (*Theobroma grandiflorum*), anón (*Annona squamosa*), breadfruit (*Artocarpus altilis*), and currant (*Ribes rubrum*) etc.

5. Conclusion

It has been shown that using a variety of non-toxic adsorbents can effectively remove several heavy metals, metalloids, and other pollutants from contaminated water and wastewater at the same time. This approach is very inexpensive, useful, ecologically benign, and effective. Mathematical techniques, including machine learning algorithms, can be used to evaluate and optimise the isotherms, thermodynamics, kinetics, and operational parameters of the adsorption processes in order to attain the best possible outcomes. In this context, inexpensive and readily

accessible agro-biowastes have become attractive options for the large-scale removal of heavy metals and metalloids. These biowastes have significant multi-chemical functional groups, surface area, cation-exchange capacity, and controlled pore architectures. Examples of these biowastes are plant fibres, fruit and vegetable peels, and byproducts from the food processing industries. The adsorbents' physical processing follows the guidelines of green chemistry. These bioadsorbents are also recyclable, which increases their sustainability and cost-effectiveness over time. Despite these developments, additional investigation is still required to maximise adsorbent performance, investigate novel materials, have a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms, and create more sustainable and economical processes for removing heavy metals from wastewater.

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